

An Efficient Encryption-Decryption Technique for Image Data Sharing in Clouds

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Abstract—The use of cloud computing has become the most desirable alternative. It's probable that the user will pay some consideration to the accuracy of the data as well as the privacy of the information. The data security that cloud computing offers can be improved in a number of ways, one of which is by making use of the several cryptographic technologies that are currently accessible. A hybrid cryptography technique for ensuring the safety of cloud data storage was provided in this work. The strategy was based on a combination of the hash function and the visual cryptography approach. When using the hash function, the user first computes the hash value or hash digest of the file, and then uploads the file to the cloud computing service for storage. In addition to that, the research presented a hybrid cryptography technique for the purpose of ensuring the safety of cloud-based data storage that has a visual cryptography approach. The data that is stored in the cloud and encrypted during the process of being stored there. The simulation is carried out with the help of MATLAB 8.3, which is the type of software that is utilized.

Keywords— Hash, VCS, Hybrid, Data, Cryptography, Security, Cloud, IOT, Server.

I. INTRODUCTION

Concerns about the safety and confidentiality of information that is stored and processed in cloud settings have grown more important as cloud computing becomes an increasingly key component of data storage and processing [1]. Due to the very nature of cloud computing, which involves the delivery of resources, applications, and services via the internet, it

is susceptible to a wide range of security issues, such as unauthorised access, data breaches, and cyberattacks. In light of this, it is necessary to implement comprehensive security methods in order to guarantee the availability, integrity, and confidentiality of the data. When it comes to protecting data in cloud settings, cryptography, which is a fundamental component of information security, plays a crucial role [2]. This ensures that sensitive information is protected even when there are possible enemies present.

Figure 1: Basic components of cloud (google)

Using mathematical techniques, cryptography is the process of converting data into an unreadable format known as ciphertext. This format can only be converted back into its original form, known as plaintext, by an individual who is in possession of the right decryption key [3]. In cloud settings, where data is often housed in data centres that are owned and operated by third parties and where the customer has minimal control over the physical infrastructure, this procedure is very necessary. Organisations are able to

safeguard data from unauthorised access by using cryptographic methods. This is possible even in the event that the store media or transmission route is compromised [4].

Within the realm of cryptography, the notion of encryption and decryption is considered to be one of the most basic concepts. The act of transforming plaintext into ciphertext by using an encryption algorithm and a key is known as encryption. This procedure renders the data unreadable to anybody who does not possess the key [5]. Using the decryption key, the ciphertext is converted back into its original plaintext form during the decryption process, which is technically the reverse of the encryption process [6]. The strength of encryption is determined by the complexity of the algorithm as well as the length of the key; in general, larger keys give higher security than their shorter counterparts.

Figure 2: Cloud Storage [1]

The usage of symmetric-key cryptography and asymmetric-key cryptography are the two basic kinds of cryptographic methods that are used in cloud security. By using the same key for both encryption and decryption, symmetric-key cryptography is able to handle massive volumes of data in a more expedient and effective manner [7]. However, the key must be securely exchanged between the sender and the recipient, which may be difficult to do in cloud systems such as those described above. On the other hand, asymmetric-key cryptography makes use of a

pair of keys, namely a public key for encryption and a private key for decryption. Because of this, there is no longer a need for the safe distribution of keys, since the public key may be freely distributed while the private key is treated as secret [8]. The use of asymmetric-key cryptography is widespread in secure communication protocols like SSL/TLS, which are essential components of cloud security.

The use of cryptographic methods includes not just encryption but also data integrity and authentication measures. These processes are essential for verifying that data has not been altered while it is being sent or stored. Hash functions, for example, take a data input and produce a hash value of a given size. This result may then be used to check whether or not the data is accurate [9]. In the event that the data is changed in any manner, the hash value will be updated, which will immediately notify the user of the tampering. Authentication is provided using digital signatures, which are another kind of cryptographic technology. These signatures allow the sender to sign a message using their private key. It is then possible for the receiver to verify the validity of the message by using the public key of the sender. This ensures that the message was in fact delivered by the sender who was claimed to have sent it [10].

The widespread use of cloud computing has resulted in the emergence of new issues in the realm of data security, notably with regard to the management of keys and the control of access. In a cloud environment, where various users and apps may access the same data, it is vital to have rigorous key management techniques in place to guarantee that only authorised users may decrypt the data. This should be done to prevent unauthorised users from accessing the data. This is something that may be accomplished via the use of methods such as attribute-based encryption (ABE) and identity-based encryption (IBE), which make it possible to implement access control rules that are more adaptable and granular. In addition, homomorphic encryption, a relatively new cryptographic technology, makes it possible to execute calculations on encrypted data without first having to

decode it. This makes it possible to process data securely in the cloud while still preserving users' privacy.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

For the goal of assuring the security of the input picture data in cloud-based Internet of Things applications, the suggested approach is based on hybrid cryptography, which takes into consideration both hash and visual cryptography techniques. This methodology was developed in order to guarantee the safety of the data.

Figure 3: Work Flow-chart

Algorithm-

Step-1: Create strings 1 and 2 in order to give server ids 1 and 2 to the respective servers.

Input data 1 and 2 were concatenated in the second step.

In the third step, the VCS encryption method is used to encrypt the output data that has been concatenated. At this point, normal text is transformed into cypher text. The cypher data was then divided into two portions, which were designated as share key 1 and share key 2. The first share key is treated as an owner identifier, and it is stored in the cloud. The second share key is treated as a user identifier, and it is also stored in the cloud.

Visual cryptography, also known as VCS, is a kind of picture encryption that provides a method of decryption that does not need the use of complicated mathematical computations.

Click on the picture that has to be uploaded to the cloud server. This is the fourth step. In the next step, encryption will be applied, and the input picture or data will be masked using XOR Masked throughout this procedure.

Creating a key matrix and verifying authenticity is the fifth step. First, make a request, then establish a URL, and if the request is successful, then upload the data to a server or cloud storage.

Proceed to the sixth step, which is to verify the cloud server before downloading the data. The owner id should be assigned to cloud(a), and the user id should be assigned to cloud(b).

Apply VCS Decryption and successfully decode the cypher data. This is the seventh step.

Send a request to the cloud to get the data or picture. This is the eighth step.

In the ninth step, the request is approved, and the data is successfully downloaded from the cloud platform.

Step ten: Create a graph and values based on the results.

(i) Hash Function or Hash Table

In the work that is being suggested, a basic index-hash table (IHT) is used to not only create the hash value of the block during the verification process but also to

record the modifications that have been made to file blocks. Our index-hash table has a structure that is comparable to that of the file block allocation table that is seen in file administration systems. In general, the index-hash table is made up of a variety of different things, including a random integer, a version number, a serial number, and a block number. Due to the fact that this form of database is distinct from the common index table, we need to make sure that every record in it is distinct from every other record in order to avoid the forging of data blocks and tags. A unique hash value is generated for each record in the database, and this value is then used to create a signature tag i using the secret key sk . This is in addition to the fact that each record in the table is utilised to produce a unique hash value. It is necessary for this sort of connection to be cryptographically safe, and we may make advantage of it in order to develop our verification protocol illustrated and the checking algorithm (ii) Visual Cryptography (VCS).

(ii) Visual Cryptography (VCS)

Figure 4: Visual_cryptography

It has been decided to divide the cypher key into two equal halves. Every single white pixel of the first key is divided into two identical tiny blocks, each of which contains 50 percent black pixels and 50 percent white pixels. When these two blocks are superimposed on top of one another, they have a perfect alignment, which results in a block that is light in colour and contains pixels that are half black and half white. Every single black pixel in the original logo is divided into two little blocks that are complimentary to one another. When these two blocks are layered on top of one another, the

outcome is a box that is all black. If each pixel in the original picture is divided in a random manner, as was mentioned before, then each individual share is a collection of blocks that is completely random. When the shares are merged, any information that was previously unknown about the original picture is now disclosed.

III. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

Implementation and simulation of the planned study task are carried out with the help of the MATLAB programme. For the simulation task, the version of MATLAB 8.3.0.532 is used. During the demonstration of the work that is being suggested, the following phases need participation:

Simulation example-

Figure 5: Verification of Server

For the purpose of validating the identification of the server and verifying that secure connection is being maintained, Figure 5 provides the fundamental information of the server.

Figure 6: Server Identity Merge

A technique that combines the identification of the server with the design key by making use of personal information is shown in Figure 6. The cloud Internet of Things system is being generated with hybrid security.

approach, this picture data has to be stored in the cloud inside the Internet of Things system.

Figure 8: key encryption after user data masked

Figure 8 illustrates the process of masking input data in order to protect data information. Following this, the key URL (Index) of the data is designed in order to store content in the cloud URL.

Figure 7: User Image_data

Presented in the form of an image is the input data presented in Figure 7. Using the hybrid encryption

Figure 9: Cloud server data store

Figure 10: Server ownership Verify

Figure 10 illustrates the procedure that has been shown to be effective whenever there is successful contact between the server and the user or when the data is successfully downloaded from the cloud server.

Figure 11: Data_Retrieve from cloud

Figure 12: Original data/image histogram

Figure 13: Reconstruct data/image histogram

Table 1: Comparison of work

Sr. No	Parameter	Previous Work [1]	Proposed Work
1	Proposed Method	Re-Encryption	Hash_Function &_VCS
2	Level of Complexity	More	Less

3	Storage of cloud	Not	Yes
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IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents hybrid cryptography to provide a practical method of protecting cloud-based data used in IoT applications. If the user follows this method, their data will be safely stored on the cloud server and may be quickly retrieved anytime needed. Users may upload a wide range of file types when they use the application-based system running on the client machine. The overarching goal of this research is to find a way to make sure that data kept on cloud servers is secure by using a combination of the VCS encryption and hash function. These algorithms will need to be tested in the future on a real-world setting or a specialised simulator to guarantee their correctness. Using and evaluating the efficacy of the different combinations of cryptographic algorithms is an additional capability. To find out whether the strategy is feasible as it is, we will look at how well it works in Internet of Things situations.

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